

Micro determination of oxprenolol hydrochloride and metoprolol tartrate with potassium dipertellurato cuprate(III) reagent

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A micro method has been developed for the determination of oxprenolol hydrochloride and metoprolol tartrate in pure form and in pharmaceutical preparation with Cu^{III} reagent. S.D. and C.V. was calculated for reproducible and accurate results. The error does not exceed $\pm 0.5\%$.

Oxprenolol and metoprolol are beta-blocker agents widely used for the treatment of hypertension, cardiac arrhythmia and angina pectoris. Oxprenolol has been determined by gas chromatography¹ and high pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC)^{2,3}. The British pharmacopia method⁴ for the assay of oxprenolol hydrochloride tablets involves a double extraction followed by evaporation of the organic solvent, dissolution of the residue in dilute hydrochloric acid and then spectrophotometric determination. Metoprolol has been determined by HPLC and gas chromatography^{5,6} oxprenolol and metoprolol are also determined with vanadium(v) reagent in acidic medium⁷. Here we describe a convenient method for determination of both drug in pure and other forms.

Results and discussion

Aliquots containing 1–5 mg drug were allowed to react with a known and excess volume of Cu^{III} reagent for various lengths of time and the unconsumed reagents were back titrated. The reacting ratio (moles of Cu^{III} per mole of drug) was calculated for each test and plotted against reaction time. It was found that both drugs required 10 min reaction time and the reacting ratios are 20 and 10 for oxprenolol hydrochloride and metoprolol tartrate respectively.

The reaction products were determined as follows : Carbon dioxide was determined by passage of the gases from the reaction vessel over sodalime. Care was taken to eliminate the presence of atmospheric carbon dioxide from the reaction vessel. This determination showed the presence of 3.5–4.0 moles of CO₂ per mole of oxprenolol and 1.5–2.0 moles of CO₂ per mole of metoprolol. Acetone was deter-

mined by distilling the reaction mixture at 56°C, collecting the distillate, adding a known amount of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (neutralized to methyl red), allowed to stand for 10–15 min and titrating the unconsumed hydroxylamine hydrochloride with alkali. The amount of acetone found corresponded to about 0.8 mole of acetone per mole of oxprenolol and metoprolol. The ammonium ion was determined according to literature method⁸. The other product in each case was extracted with diethyl ether and analysed for methoxy group content. Assay of pure samples of oxprenolol hydrochloride and metoprolol tartrate and their pharmaceutical preparations viz. tablets and injection was achieved by recommended procedure with an error not exceeding $\pm 0.5\%$.

Experimental

Reagent : Analytical reagent grade chemicals were used whenever possible, unless otherwise stated.

Potassium dipertellurato cuprate(III) reagent (0.035 M) : Copper sulphate (7.0805 g, E. Merck), potassium tellurite (15.8630 g, B.D.H.) and potassium hydroxide (40 g, E. Merck) were added to 400 ml of distilled water in a 500 ml conical flask. The mixture was shaken thoroughly and then heated on a hot plate for ca. 40 min, cooled to room temperature, and volume made up after filtration.

Pure drugs : Accurately weighted 50 mg amount of oxprenolol and metoprolol were dissolved in 10 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid and diluted to volume with distilled water in a 50 ml standard flask. Tablets were ground and known weight of the powder, equivalent to about 50 mg of

Note

Table I. Micro determination of oxiprenolol hydrochloride and metoprolol tartarate in pure form and in their pharmaceutical preparations

Sample	Amount taken (mg)	Stoichio- metry	(Reaction time 10 min)			
			Amount found (mg)	Error %	S D (mg)	C V %
1 Oxiprenolol (Pure sample)	1 0000	20	1 0013	+ 0 13	0 0016	0 1598
	3 0000		3 0063	+ 0 21		
	5 0000		4 9870	- 0 26		
(a) Oxiprenolol tablet (Ciba-Geigy, 40 mg)	1 0000	20	1 0022	+ 0 22	0 0080	0 2665
	3 0000		3 0054	+ 0 18		
	5 0000		4 9845	- 0 31		
(b) Oxiprenolol injection Ciba-Geigy, 2 mg dry ampoule)	1 0000	20	0 9990	- 0 10	0 0038	0 0762
	3 0000		2 9919	- 0 27		
	5 0000		4 9795	- 0 41		
2 Metoprolol (Pure sample)	1 0000	10	1 0016	+ 0 16	0 0017	0 1700
	3 0000		3 0048	+ 0 16		
	5 0000		5 0110	+ 0 22		
(a) Metoprolol tablet (Astra-IDL, 100 mg)	1 0000	10	0 9988	- 0 12	0 0035	0 1165
	3 0000		3 0051	+ 0 17		
	5 0000		4 9845	- 0 31		
(b) Metoprolol injection (Astra-IDL, 1 mg/ml)	1 0000	10	0 9985	- 0 15	0 0094	1 1881
	3 0000		2 9988	- 0 04		
	5 0000		4 9890	- 0 22		

the pure drug was dissolved in 10 ml of conc. H₂SO₄ and accurately diluted to 50 ml in the same way as in the case of pure drugs. The contents of the ampoules were dissolved in 10 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid and diluted to known volume with distilled water to give a solution with drug concentration of about 1 mg/ml.

Procedure :

Aliquots containing 1–5 mg of the sample were taken in a 150 ml Erlenmeyer flask fitted with an air condenser. 10 ml of Cu^{III} reagent was added to the sample in the flask and the content was shaken and kept on a hot plate for reflux for 10 min. The volume of the reaction mixture was maintained constant by adding distilled water from the top of the condenser. After the reaction was over the content was cooled to room temperature. The unused Cu^{III} reagent was estimated by the arsenite method⁹. A blank was also run simultaneously using all reagents except the sample. The amount of the sample was calculated by the following expression,

$$\text{mg of sample} = \frac{(B - S) MW}{N}$$

where, B = volume of iodine solution consumed in the blank titration, S = volume of iodine solution consumed in the test sample titration, M = molarity of the iodine solution, W = molecular weight of the drug, N = number of moles of Cu^{III} consumed per mole of drug

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